

Efficient Edge-to-Cloud Workload Management

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Disclaimer

The content of this deliverable has been prepared in compliance with the requirements of the European Commission for the management, organization, documentation, and sharing of research data generated or collected during the course of the ENACT project. The nature of this deliverable is public (PU), hence its content can be shared with consortium partners and general public.

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Content

- 1. Executive Summary.....4**
- 2. Introduction4**
 - 2.1 Purpose and scope of the deliverable..... 5
 - 2.2 Relation to other WPs and tasks 5
 - 2.3 Structure of the deliverable..... 5
- 3. ENACT Data.....5**
 - 3.1 Internal Documents..... 5
 - 3.2 Pilot Data..... 6
 - 3.2.1 Use Case #1 - Distributed Media and Entertainment Content Management [MOG]..... 6
 - 3.2.2 Use Case #2 – Enhanced Live Experience: Transforming rowing Regattas Flag La Concha Tracking with VR and XR Technologies..... 8
 - 3.2.3 Use Case #3 - Hyper-Distributed Data Processing for Fujitsu’s Mobility Digital Twin Initiative [FUJ] 8
 - 3.3 Generated Data..... 10
 - 3.4 Dissemination and Promotion Data 10
- 4. ENACT Project and FAIR Data Principles 12**
 - 4.1 Making data Findable, including provisions for metadata 12
 - 4.1.1 Assigning a globally unique and persistent identifier for data and metadata 12
 - 4.1.2 Description of data with rich metadata..... 12
 - 4.1.3 Identifiers for the metadata..... 12
 - 4.1.4 Searchable resource for (meta)data 12
 - 4.2 Making data openly Accessible 12
 - 4.2.1 Identifier for retrieving meta (data) using a standardized communication protocol..... 12
 - 4.2.2 Accessibility of metadata in absence of data..... 13
 - 4.3 Making data Interoperable 13
 - 4.3.1 Formal and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation of (meta)data 13
 - 4.3.2 Usage of vocabulary for meta(data) based on FAIR principles..... 13
 - 4.3.3 Qualified reference to other meta(data)..... 14
 - 4.4 Increase data Re-use (through clarifying licenses) 14
 - 4.4.1 Description of (meta)data with accurate attributes..... 14

- 5. Data security 14**
- 6. Gender considerations..... 16**
 - 6.1 Gender Dimension..... 16
 - 6.1.1 Gender Analysis..... 17
 - 6.1.2 Gender Survey 17
 - 6.1.3 Analysis of the Gender Survey and Further Steps22
- 7. Ethics consideration in ENACT23**
 - 7.1 Ethics for Trustworthy AI.....24
 - 7.1.1 T5.1: AI Models for Optimal Performance Predictions in the Compute Continuum [CERTH]26
 - 7.1.2 T5.2: Graph Neural Networks for Scheduling and Dynamic Optimisation of Hyper-Distributed Applications [UPV].....29
 - 7.1.3 T5.3 GNN & RL-based Orchestrator for Dynamic Deployments in the Compute Continuum [UNP]32
 - 7.1.4 T5.4 Virtual Environment for Training, Retraining and Recalibration of AI Models [ICE]32
 - 7.2 Analysis of AI self-assessment for the overall ENACT project34
- 8. Conclusion35**
- 9. List of Acronyms36**

List of Tables

- Table 1. UC1 Sports Events Broadcast Video Data Description..... 6
- Table 2. UC1 Sports Events Broadcast Video Positional Metadata Description 7
- Table 3. UC3 MaaS Real world vehicle and road data 9
- Table 4. Main repositories for storing different types of data..... 11
- Table 5. Gender Statistics 17

1. Executive Summary

This is the first version of the ENACT Data Management Plan (DMP). This is a 'live' document and will be updated continuously until the end of the project. Task 1.4 (Data Management and Governance, Trustworthy AI, Regulatory, Societal, Ethical and Gender Issues) leading this deliverable aims at monitoring the data generated by the project, maintaining its privacy and confidentiality based on the legal and ethical principles.

The objective of this deliverable is to help project partners in dealing with data generated and used in the ENACT project by providing a framework for data management. This framework will enable the project partners to effectively manage, store, and share data in a systematic manner and in this way to enhance the quality, security, privacy, and reliability of research data. This framework will also help partners to address the needs of data re-use and sharing considering Horizon Europe requirements of open research data and implement relevant legislations such as General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) data principles.

2. Introduction

In Horizon Europe projects, DMP is a live document that is set up in the beginning of the project and is continuously updated until the end. DMP aims to provide information about data generation, processing, gathering, and storing.

This deliverable provides following information about the ENACT data management in accordance with FAIR data principles:

1. List the procedure for handling the research data during and after the project's completion.
2. List the type of gathered, processed, and generated data in the project.
3. List the datasets that will be accessible to the public.
4. List the methods for organization and preservation of project data (including after end of project).

ENACT aims to exchange data between multiple stakeholders in the edge-cloud computing. For this purpose, collection, processing, sharing, and reusing the data requires particular attention to ensure the security and privacy of data generated and used in the project.

In ENACT, resource management for edge and cloud is performed for dynamic portability of hyper-distributed applications to introduce a Cognitive Computing Continuum (CCC). Dynamic graph models are developed to capture the real time information of distributed edge and cloud resource. The AI models i.e. Graph Neural Networks (GNN) and Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) uses the graph models to determine optimal deployment configuration. ENACT also develops an innovative Application Programming Model (APM) through which platform agnostic applications can be developed. These applications will have the capability to self-determine their optimal deployment and execution configuration utilizing the available resources in the CCC. ENACT CCC solutions will be demonstrated in three use cases (UCs).

2.1 Purpose and scope of the deliverable

In ENACT, overall project management and coordination is done in Work Package (WP1). Task 1.4 (Data Management and Governance, Trustworthy AI, Regulatory, Societal, Ethical and Gender Issues) of WP1 produces this live document of DMP which considers Horizon Europe's framework for open research data and provides concrete guidelines to project partners with regards to the management and utilization of data. This DMP deliverable will be continually updated during the project and the final version of the deliverable will be submitted in M36.

2.2 Relation to other WPs and tasks

This deliverable contains information gathered from the use case (UC) partners (in WP3) of the ENACT project, the AI solution provider partners (in WP5) and finally from all partners about gender analysis (current status), alongside dissemination related data (WP8). The gathered information and datasets are described in detail to show the type of data collected, generated, and used during the lifespan of the project.

2.3 Structure of the deliverable

This deliverable is structured as follows: Section 3 describes data generated from the project partners including use cases. Section 4 details the procedure to follow in compliance with FAIR data principles. Section 5 provides the data security considerations in the project (in this early stage). Gender considerations are described in Section 6. Ethical aspects and guidelines for trustworthy AI are included in Section 7. Finally, Section 8 concludes this deliverable.

3. ENACT Data

In this section, various types of data generated or available in the ENACT project are presented. Based on the data availability in different areas, the following four main classes of data are defined:

1. Internal documents
2. Pilot data
3. Generated data
4. Dissemination and promotion data

3.1 Internal Documents

Different documents produced by project partners during the course of the ENACT project as part of their research and technology development activities in various tasks and WPs will be stored as internal documents. The types of documents produced will include deliverables, such as this data management plan, scientific publications, technical documentation, dissemination and communication material (e.g. brochures, flyers, whitepapers etc.), and Consortium agreement (CA). These documents are shared in PDF, docx, xlsx and ppt format. These types of documents will be stored internally by the project team in a dedicated Next Cloud password-protected repository (2 factor authentication is supported), setup by the project coordinator CERTH, which is accessible by consortium partners only.

3.2 Pilot Data

This section describes the Use Cases datasets that will be generated and used in the scope of the ENACT project. The purpose of this activity is to gather information for ENACT deliverable, D1.3 “Data Management Plan”. The information gathered will encompass what pilot data will be generated in the course of the project but also what data exists already. It will also capture how data it will be used and made available to the partners and the public. The aim is to ensure that all legal and ethical requirements are followed. Information related to the FAIR data processing principles is also gathered from pilots in the following tables. These will be revised in the next version of this deliverable.

All pilot partners contributed to this section and provided the relevant information about the datasets that are being used in their systems or can be used for the training and testing of the AI solutions in the ENACT project.

3.2.1 Use Case #1 - Distributed Media and Entertainment Content Management [MOG]

The aim of this pilot is to adopt ENACT CCC orchestration methodology and Application Programming Models and apps for the distribution of the existing content processing system of MOG. This will enable the distributed processing and the available edge-cloud infrastructure can be utilized. ENACT will help this UC to process of large volume of audio-video content and ensure interrupted broadcast across the world.

Table 1. UC1 Sports Events Broadcast Video Data Description

Data Title:	Sports Events Broadcast Video Data
Data ID	Sports-Events-Dataset
Description:	Multimedia Data from sports events
Owner:	MOG / Broadcasters
Data Source (device, cloud, system etc.)	Device (cameras)
Data access, sharing and licensing	By default, data will be shared for internal (with respect to the project scope) use only. A sample might be available online, but no final decision has been made yet.
Class (IPR – open, private, confidential)	Private data
Data type (Integer, Float, String etc.):	Unstructured video
Data format (Json, CSV, TXT etc.):	MPEG-TS
Access Protocol:	URL generated on demand for download

Data size:	300Gb
Data storage/Repository:	MOG File Storage
Personal information:	Yes (Athletes body/face)
Data Security Needs (e.g. data needs to be anonymized, or encrypted or not shared outside the project etc.):	Data should not be shared outside the project
Regulatory Constraint Requirements (e.g. not stored outside EU or acquisition of consent):	Not stored outside EU
Are you reusing the data or is the data reuseable? If YES, which data and how?	Yes, the videos are reusable
Data preservation period (is there an expiry date for the data?):	No
How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?	Throughout the project. No guarantee can be given about the availability of meta data after the project
Describe Unique and persistent identifier (e.g., DOI, URI)?	MOGUC_YYYYMMDD_Team1vTeam2
Describe what type of rich metadata is used (e.g., title, creator, keywords)?	Title(teams), duration, format, resolution, frame rate
Is the data quality and reliability assessed and documented (e.g., validation, provenance)? If yes, how?	No
Is the data interoperable? If yes, mention the usage of any standard vocabularies/data models/ontologies	Yes, the videos are in a widely accepted formats

Table 2. UC1 Sports Events Broadcast Video Positional Metadata Description

Data Title:	Sports Events Broadcast Video Positional Metadata
Data ID	Sports-Events-Metadata
Description:	Metadata generated from sports events broadcasts regarding players positional information. This metadata will be generated for every frame of the videos dataset Table 1. UC1 Sports Events Broadcast Video Data Description in Table 1
Owner:	MOG / Broadcasters
Data Source (device, cloud, system etc.)	System
Data access, sharing and licensing	By default, data will be shared for internal (with respect to the project scope) use only. A sample might be available online, but no final decision has been made yet.
Class (IPR – open, private, confidential)	Private data

Data type (Integer, Float, String etc.):	String, Integer
Data format (Json, CSV, TXT etc.):	JSON, XML
Access Protocol:	URL generated on demand for download
Data size:	For 1 video, depends on the video events, however the metadata file it should be around 40MB.
Data storage/Repository:	MOG File Storage
Personal information:	No
Data Security Needs (e.g. data needs to be anonymized, or encrypted or not shared outside the project etc.):	Data should not be shared outside the project
Regulatory Constraint Requirements (e.g. not stored outside EU or acquisition of consent):	Not stored outside EU.
Are you reusing the data or is the data reuseable? If YES, which data and how?	The data is reusable for other tasks such as creating extra visual content.
Data preservation period (is there an expiry date for the data?):	No
How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?	Throughout the project. No
Describe Unique and persistent identifier (e.g., DOI, URI)?	None
Describe what type of rich metadata is used (e.g., title, creator, keywords)?	Title, date, schema version, schema URL, video id
Is the data quality and reliability assessed and documented (e.g., validation, provenance)? If yes, how?	No
Is the data interoperable? If yes, mention the usage of any standard vocabularies/data models/ontologies	Yes, the metadata format vocabulary definition is part of WP2T1.

3.2.2 Use Case #2 – Enhanced Live Experience: Transforming rowing Regattas Flag La Concha Tracking with VR and XR Technologies

Details about UC2 will be included in the next version of DMP which is due in M36. The preliminary information about this pilot will also be released in the periodic report (due in M09).

3.2.3 Use Case #3 – Hyper-Distributed Data Processing for Fujitsu’s Mobility Digital Twin Initiative [FUJ]

The goal of this use-case is to develop distributed deployment configurations for Fujitsu’s Mobility Digital Twin services to enable their execution in a cloud-to-edge continuum. Distributed management of data by mobile devices will be achieved by adopting APM portable apps paradigm. This use-case will develop an innovative way to deploy and manage distributed data coverage control function to significantly decrease data duplications in the edge-cloud continuum.

As part of the use-case, a real-time road condition monitoring system will be developed that integrates data from multiple sources and provides up-to-date information on key parameters such as speed, traffic signals, accidents, and congestion for further analysis and processing.

Table 3. UC3 MaaS Real world vehicle and road data

Data Title:	MaaS Real world vehicle and road data
Data ID	Maas-001
Description:	Vehicle sensor data road and traffic data
Owner:	To be investigated
Data Source (device, cloud, system etc.)	Device, system
Data access, sharing and licensing	By default, data will be shared for internal (with respect to the project scope) use only. A sample might be available online, but no final decision has been made yet.
Class (IPR – open, private, confidential)	Open and Private data
Data type (Integer, Float, String etc.):	String/Integer,Float (key=>value)
Data format (Json, CSV, TXT etc.):	Json
Access Protocol:	Specific software, API to access the data. Internally data being shared using Kafka’s queues.
Data size:	MB/GB
Data storage/Repository:	API/Kafka
Personal information:	No
Data Security Needs (e.g. data needs to be anonymized, or encrypted or not shared outside the project etc.):	Implement processes of real-time and historical location data anonymization
Regulatory Constraint Requirements (e.g. not stored outside EU or acquisition of consent):	Data will be stored within the EU
Are you reusing the data or is the data reuseable? If YES, which data and how?	Yes, we want to use road and traffic data available from public resources
Data preservation period (is there an expiry date for the data?):	No
How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?	To be investigated
Describe Unique and persistent identifier (e.g., DOI, URI)?	OID
Describe what type of rich metadata is used (e.g., title, creator, keywords)?	keywords
Is the data quality and reliability assessed and documented (e.g., validation, provenance)? If yes, how?	To be investigated

Is the data interoperable? If yes, mention the usage of any standard vocabularies/data models/ontologies

To be investigated

3.3 Generated Data

This category of data covers the data generated by technical activities such as AI models, Dynamic Graph Models, Application Programming Module (APM), and telemetry data. Dynamic graph models will use real time and historic information about distributed edge and cloud resources and generate data about connectivity types, energy consumption and dependencies. These graphs are used as input to AI models which will generate data about optimal deployment configuration. This data will be stored and exchanged between the partners in csv, sav, zip, npy, py, h5, pb, json, owl, rdf data formats.

Source code for different components of the ENACT also comes under this category. Source code management will be provided by ENACT partner, Eclipse, in Eclipse Research Lab¹. This is the place where the Eclipse Research community comes together to collaborate in open source. The projects are developed openly in a straightforward manner, initiating the partners to the Eclipse Development process.

ENACT project has setup a Gitlab infrastructure in Eclipse Research Labs, publicly available², where the open-source code developed under the project is stored, allowing the engagement with the developer community from day one.

3.4 Dissemination and Promotion Data

This section describes the data generated by dissemination and promotion activities. The repositories used for storing data and access to the public are also defined.

Type of Data Generated:

The project will produce a variety of data through its dissemination and promotion efforts, aiming to communicate its findings effectively and engage stakeholders. These data types include:

1. **Publications:** Scientific articles, conference papers, reports, and white papers generated throughout the project duration.
2. **Presentations:** Slide decks, posters, and oral presentations delivered at conferences, workshops, and other events.
3. **Multimedia Content:** Videos, infographics, and animations created to communicate project outcomes in a visually engaging manner.
4. **Training Materials:** Workshops, webinars, and training sessions developed to educate stakeholders about project methodologies and results.

¹ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs>

² <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project>

5. **Social Media Metrics:** Data on engagement, reach, and impressions from social media platforms used for project promotion and communication.
6. **Website Analytics:** Traffic data, user interactions, and download statistics from the project website.

Repositories for Storing Data:

To ensure accessibility and transparency, the project will use various repositories for storing and disseminating the generated data. These repositories are selected based on their suitability for different types of data and their alignment with open science principles. Below are the main repositories used:

Table 4. Main repositories for storing different types of data

Repository	Description	Types of Data Stored	Accessibility
Open Access Journals	Peer-reviewed publications	Scientific articles, conference papers	Publicly accessible
Institutional Repository	Hosted by the project's affiliated institution	Reports, white papers, presentations	Publicly accessible
Conference Proceedings	Conference-specific repositories	Conference papers, presentations	Publicly accessible through conference or publisher websites
Project Website	Dedicated project website	Multimedia content, training materials	Publicly accessible at https://enact-horizon.eu/
Social Media Platforms	Twitter, LinkedIn, etc.	Social media metrics	Publicly accessible https://www.linkedin.com/in/enact-horizon-1798122b8/ https://twitter.com/ENACT_horizon
Data Repositories	Disciplinary or general repositories	Raw data, supplementary materials	NextCloud (Access granted on request)
Zenodo Repository	ENACT project repository	Open-access journals and proceedings, pre-prints, datasets and documents relevant to project	Publicly accessible

By employing these repositories and accessibility measures, the project maximizes the dissemination and impact of its findings, fostering collaboration, and promoting transparency in research.

4. ENACT Project and FAIR Data Principles

In ENACT project, FAIR data principles will be applied to all types of data including pilot data, generated data and project documents.

4.1 Making data Findable, including provisions for metadata

ENACT project will be applying the following four sub-principles to make data and metadata findable:

4.1.1 Assigning a globally unique and persistent identifier for data and metadata

Globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID) shall be provided to ensure the findability of research and pilot-related data. Public registration of identifiers schemes must be done to ensure unambiguous identification and interoperability across different systems, applications, and domains.

4.1.2 Description of data with rich metadata

The metadata shall be descriptive and provide comprehensive details about the data including information such as relationships, provenance, quality, characteristics, and conditions.

4.1.3 Identifiers for the metadata

Unambiguous and unique identifiers shall be provided within the metadata file of the dataset for associating the dataset and metadata as these are in different files.

4.1.4 Searchable resource for (meta)data

Persistent identifiers of the resources shall be provided which are findable on various search engines.

In particular, ENACT plans the use of metadata in components related to Data Space/Storage and ENACT Apps. The Data Manager component of ENACT Data Space will use metadata for various resources description, registration and discovery based on concepts of IDSA Metadata Broker³ and GAIA-X Catalogs⁴. Furthermore, YAML representation will be used from ENACT APM-based Apps for description of configuration files and cases where data is being stored or transmitted (related to apps). It is a common practice to use YAML to add metadata, such as title, tags, and descriptions etc. in order to Markdown documents. Metadata are also available in some of the available pilot data as described in chapter 3 of this document.

4.2 Making data openly Accessible

4.2.1 Identifier for retrieving meta (data) using a standardized communication protocol

4.2.1.1 Free and open-source protocol

The project's data and metadata shall be accessible through free and open-source access protocol.

³ https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-knowledgebase/v/ids-ram-4/layers-of-the-reference-architecture-model/3-layers-of-the-reference-architecture-model/3_5_0_system_layer/3_5_4_metadata_broker

⁴ <https://gaia-x.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Gaia-x-Architecture-Document-22.04-Release.pdf>

4.2.1.2 *Applying authentication and authorization procedures*

Appropriate authentication and authorization procedures shall be considered in cases where datasets are confidential or under restriction.

4.2.2 **Accessibility of metadata in absence of data**

Persistence of metadata over time is mandatory for long-term accessibility. Data descriptors shall be provided so that metadata is discoverable even in absence of data.

ENACT will adopt Data Spaces paradigm that metadata/data can be done publicly available or under specific conditions based on sharing policies specified by the Data Provider/Owner. Corresponding authentication/authorization mechanisms from data space artefacts such as data connectors will be used alongside Identity and Access management components, such as Keycloak⁵.

4.3 **Making data Interoperable**

4.3.1 **Formal and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation of (meta)data**

A set of well-defined data models will be developed as the formal, broadly applicable language for knowledge representation, which will be used for (meta) data interoperability purposes among all ENACT platform components.

The ENACT compute continuum data models shall facilitate the representation of (a) applications or services and their characteristics, (b) the available computing continuum resources and devices and their capabilities, and (c) the telemetry data stemming from the execution of applications in the infrastructure. The models will provide structure, vocabularies and terminology for the description of these concepts, and will be used for data communication and interoperability purposes among the ENACT platform components. The representation of resources and devices shall be compatible with the OASIS Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications (TOSCA)⁶, a widely used industry standard, so as to enable interoperability with external infrastructure. Further adoption of widely used standards, such as the Unified Modelling Language (UML)⁷ for representing telemetry data and the Open Workflow Description Language (OpenWDL)⁸ for describing computational workflows comprising multiple tasks and dependencies, will be considered wherever applicable for facilitating interoperability with third party systems.

4.3.2 **Usage of vocabulary for meta(data) based on FAIR principles**

As part of the aforementioned ENACT CC models, commonly used vocabulary and terminology shall be used for data and metadata that are themselves following FAIR principles guidelines.

⁵ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

⁶ Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications (TOSCA) Version 1.0 OASIS Standard, <http://docs.oasis-open.org/tosca/TOSCA/v1.0/TOSCA-v1.0.html>

⁷ Object Management Group. Unified Modelling Language (UML). OMG Specifications

⁸ Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH). Workflow Description Language (OpenWDL). <https://github.com/ga4gh/workflow-execution-service-schemas>

4.3.3 Qualified reference to other meta(data)

Appropriate reference to additional metadata resource shall be provided which will enrich description by interlinking between datasets and provide more detail about a particular resource.

4.4 Increase data Re-use (through clarifying licenses)

4.4.1 Description of (meta)data with accurate attributes

4.4.1.1 Accessible data usage license

The conditions to re-use the data and metadata shall be provided through a license document.

4.4.1.2 Detailed provenance

The overall provenance of the data processed during the project shall be provided using ontologies and state-of-the-art (SOTA) methods.

4.4.1.3 Domain relevant community standards

Validation techniques for metadata guidelines established for different communities to maximize usability of the shared data shall be implemented. Standard organizations such as GAIA-X⁹ and European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)¹⁰ will be considered for collaboration.

5. Data security

Cybersecurity requirements need to be incorporated in information technology (IT) systems to provide secure services. The directive on cybersecurity across EU i.e. NIS 2 Directive¹¹ requires Member States to incorporate cybersecurity risk reduction methods for maintaining essential services. Cyber Resilience Act¹² advises to consider security of ICT products at the design and development stage. For systems that process personal data the implications of GDPR need to be considered. GDPR requires implementation of appropriate data controller and processors incorporating security measure such as pseudonymization and encryption tools¹³. Ensuring compliance with data protection laws and regulations is the responsibility of a data controller.

⁹ Gaia-X – a new proposal for the next generation of data infrastructure: 'an open, transparent and secure digital ecosystem, where data and services can be made available, collated and shared in an environment of trust. See What is Gaia-X?' available at: <https://www.datainfrastructure.eu/GAIA/Navigation/EN/Home/home.html>

¹⁰ EOSC – A multidisciplinary data infrastructure developed by the European Commission. A key objective of the EOSC is to federate scientific data and digital infrastructures existing across disciplines and EU Member States for data exploitation. See European Commission, Commission Staff Working Document – Implementation Roadmap for the European Open Science Cloud, SWD (2018) 83 final. See also, Sarah Jones and Jean-François Abramatic, European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Strategic Implementation Plan (European Union 2019), available at: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/78ae5276-ae8e-11e9-9d01-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

¹¹ Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, amending Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 and Directive (EU) 2018/1972, and repealing Directive (EU) 2016/1148 (NIS 2 Directive).

¹² Cyber Resilience Act, available at: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/cyber-resilience-act> (Accessed 10 December 2022).

¹³ Art. 32(1)(a) GDPR.

Implementing a data controller is the responsibility of the pilot partner processing personal data. Data breach of personal data must be reported by the data controller to the authority within 72 hours¹⁴. The details about the breach and their consequences together with mitigation action must be documented by the controller¹⁵. It is the responsibility of all project partners to take appropriate action to maintain the security of the platform. The participants in the project should implement a continuity plan by assessing the impact caused by the cyber intrusion and prevent any future attacks¹⁶.

GDPR lists the following provisions for securing personal data:

1. Data minimization: This principle emphasizes to limit use of data only for achieving a specific task.
2. Protection of personal data by design and default: requirements for privacy and data protection should be integrated into the design of the information technology (IT) systems.
3. Data protection and impact assessments (DPIAs): This principle is an extension of the “Secure by design” concept which is achieved by assessing impact of any new data processing on the security of personal data.

ENACT involves personal data processing in UC1 (Distributed Media and Entertainment Content Management) which will be performed in accordance with following provisions:

1. GDPR (Regulation (EU) 2016/679).
2. Universal Declaration of Human Rights and Convention 108.
3. National laws.

These provisions will be discussed in detail with UC1 in the first workshop which will be conducted in M10 of the project by DS4.

Besides, data security for personal data processing in accordance with GDPR rules. ENACT CCC also uses a dedicated vertical layer for secure communication of interoperable access to distributed resources. This is achieved in Task 4.1 (Zero-Touch Provisioning, Networking and Configuration of Distributed Resources) through a security module based on Next Generation- Software Defined Network (NG-SDN) which performs decentralized telemetry service monitoring across multiple endpoints to detect security vulnerabilities during orchestration and scheduling. Moreover, the development of Zero Touch Provisioning (ZTP) service is considered in ENACT T4.1 for accessing new data and compute nodes. A data preprocessing module and data transformation module that is based on Extract, Transform, Load (ETL) e.g. Jolt which provides a set of data transformation techniques to perform JSON to JSON transform. ENACT will utilize Jolt for handling heterogeneous data and modeling data on existing standards hence maintaining interoperability principle.

Furthermore, ENACT aims to promote project data following FAIR principles by utilizing secure data space connector based on the governance principles as described in International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) and GAIA-X. There is a dedicated ENACT task, T4.4 (Secure and Sovereign

¹⁴ The GDPR defines a “personal data breach” in Article 4(12) as: a breach of security leading to the accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorized disclosure of, or access to, personal data transmitted, stored or otherwise processed.”

¹⁵ Article 33 GDPR.

¹⁶ See Guidelines of personal data breach notification under Regulation 2016/679 adopted on 3 October 2017. As last revised and adopted on 6 February 2018. Article 20 Working Party.

Distributed Data Storage) for secure and trusted data exchange in distributed nodes. Open-source available Dataspace Connector (DIN SPEC 27070 standard) will be utilized to develop a data and object space connector. In ENACT, data sharing is brought to the next level by implementing sharing of objects between the applications in the dataspace. This will in turn make the implementation of application faster by utilizing dataspace as distributed data store. T4.4 will also provide identity and access management mechanisms for participants and components to authorize user access to the services deployed in ENACT.

Besides this, ENACT also utilizes a Distributed Data Manager component in Task 5.3 (GNN & RL-based Orchestrator for Dynamic Deployments in the Compute Continuum) in a data layer which supports creation and management of entities in the edge cloud compute continuum. Data sharing and storage, being the important part for distributed data and object storage will be handled by persistence of objects through allowing object storage in a standard format which can be reused in subsequent executions. This eliminates data mapping to objects in the Database Management System (DBMS). As a general principle, in ENACT, data is kept close to the computation to minimize the security risks and provide authentication to real-time data streams.

The security of data generated and produced within the project is ensured by the use of trusted repositories such as Zenodo¹⁷. Zenodo will be used to store the datasets, technical deliverable and scientific publications. These platforms assign DOIs making it findable in accordance with FAIR principles. It is the responsibility of the partner uploading particular data to also provide information about metadata and description of tools for data validation and reuse in the repository. The research data should be well-documented and license information will be provided. ENACT will follow Attribution (CC BY) and Creative Commons Zero (CCO) license for management of research data. In accordance with this licensing scheme, ENACT facilitates the reuse/sharing of research output by allowing users to re-use and commercialize the project output by giving attribution to the original creator.

6. Gender considerations

6.1 Gender Dimension

In March 2020 the European Commission published its vision for combating gender inequality in the document 'A Union of Equality: Gender Quality Strategy 2020-2025'¹⁸. It sets out the policy objectives and key actions aiming at achieving a gender equal Europe by ending gender-based violence, challenging gender stereotypes, closing gender gaps in the labour market, achieving equal participation across different sectors of the economy, addressing the gender pay and pension gaps, closing the gender care gap and achieving gender balance in decision-making.

In order for the ENACT project to align with this strategy, gender statistics has been collected for each project beneficiary and the gender analysis has been presented below. In addition, a survey has been carried out aiming to capture some initial feedback on gender-related issues among the project staff; the content of the survey and analysis have been also presented further below.

¹⁷ <https://zenodo.org/>

¹⁸ eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0152

6.1.1 Gender Analysis

Table 5. Gender Statistics

Beneficiary	Total Number of Researchers on the project		Total number of staff on the project other than Researchers		Total number of staff on the project	
	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male
CERTH	0	3	0	0	0	3
UPV	1	2	0	0	1	2
ICE	0	2	1	1	1	3
ECL	1	3	3	5	4	8
MOG	1	4	1	0	2	4
UNP	0	0	2	5	2	5
DNET	1	2	2	1	3	3
DS4	2	2			2	2
FDI	0	2	0	2	0	4
INNO	2	1	0	0	2	1
SIE	4	2	1	1	3	3
ICCS	2	4	0	0	2	4
UOWM	2	4	1	1	3	5
ARC	2	2	5	5	7	7
FUJ	0	2	1	1	1	3
Total	18	35	17	22	33	57

6.1.2 Gender Survey

The gender survey has been designed and provided by DS4 to all partners in the project. The survey has been created by using MS Forms and the responses have been captured anonymously. The analysis of the survey is presented below:

Total Responses Received: 20

Question 1: What is your gender?

Figure 1: Question 1 Answers

Question 2: Have you worked on a European project before?

Figure 2: Question 2 Answers

Question 2.1: If yes, have any of the projects dealt with any gender-related issues? Please specify

- **Summary of responses:**
 - Other EU projects have developed Gender equality plan in 80% of the project there was gender balance ensured
 - In other projects gender statistics were collected.
 - The projects collected statistics of partners and aimed for certain KPIs (e.g. increase women's participation in the project).
 - yes, every project I worked on has collected gender statistics from their beneficiaries.
 - Yes in the project ASSIST-IoT they collected gender statistics to create a gender equality plan.
 - In the EC funded ZDMP project, a survey of gender balance in the project was carried out to prepare gender equality plan for the project.
 - Yes, all of the recent projects have gathered gender-related statistics, but few informed about policies or created an equality plan.
 - There have been gender statistics but not a gender equality plan yet
 - Yes, in some of them there was a requirement to submit the partner's gender policies and plans and to be disseminated among the employees.

Question 3: Are you aware of any gender-related policies by the European Commission?

Figure 3: Question 3 Answers

Question 3.1: If yes, please elaborate

- **Summary of responses:**

- ending gender-based violence
- challenging gender stereotypes
- closing gender gaps in the labour market
- achieving equal participation across different sectors of the economy
- addressing the gender pay and pension gaps
- closing the gender care gap
- achieving gender balance in decision-making
- Work-life Balance of parents.
- payment transparency to minimize the gender payment gap
- I am aware of the gender-related policy; however, I would like to know more about this.
- I am aware of the EC Gender Equality Strategy and its key objectives and action points
- I am aware that there is the gender equality strategy. I don't know the details. In my team, we have over 50% of female colleagues and always aim to have a balanced mix of genders in project activities, especially in the dissemination events.
- Yes, but it would be nice to refresh our knowledge on the specifics or any updates.

Question 3.2: If no, would you be interested to be informed about this?

Figure 4: Question 3.2 Answers

Question 4: Do you think it is important that we discuss gender-related topics on the ENACT project?

Figure 5: Question 4 Answers

Question 4.1: If yes, please suggest any actions that we should take on the project in order to increase awareness about and address any gender inequality, discrimination or intimidation

- **Summary of responses:**
 - promote the participation of women in research output presentations (e.g. conferences, workshops)
 - establish gender equality KPIs
 - Potential ideas/actions include the organization of a webinar and/or short informative material.
 - adopt gender-neutral language. I have often heard, although it may be unintentionally, that people refer to a user as 'he', rather than use plural 'they'
 - review deliverables for gender-neutral language - the same suggestion as above - change he/she/his/her to they/their
 - create a well-defined process for project staff to report on any incidents of gender discrimination or intimidation and for these incidents to be addressed

- While I think that there are no major gender issues in the projects like ENACT, I believe it's important to discuss and hear opinions of everyone involved as views are not always the same when it comes to gender equality. Such discussions can help improve mutual understanding.
- A presentation/workshop about gender-related issues might be a good idea.
- Promote gender equality within the project

Question 5: Are you aware of any policy documents that exist in your organisation aiming to address gender inequality and improve gender balance?

Figure 6: Question 5 Answers

Question 5.1: If yes, please elaborate what these documents are and how they have been provided to you.

- **Summary of responses:**
 - we have gender equality plan, yearly evaluation
 - 70 % of our top management are represented by women (hi tech company)
 - We address this point in our code of conduct document
 - Our company has provided me with its Equality and Diversity Policy document
 - There's a Gender Equality Plan for our organization.

Question 5.2: If no, do you think that it would be good for your organisation to have such documents and provide them to their employees?

Figure 7: Question 5.2 Answers

Question 6: Have you ever had any adverse gender-related personal experience in your organisation?

Figure 8: Question 6 Answers

Question 6.1: If yes, what was done?

- **Summary of responses:**
 - Nothing
 - I followed the organisation process and reported the incident

Question 7: Please write any further comments/suggestions you wish to make on this topic.

- All gender identities should be considered in relation to this topic, not only the prevalent ones (male/female).

6.1.3 Analysis of the Gender Survey and Further Steps

- We start by acknowledging the ratio of men/women who completed the survey 75%/25% demonstrating that the gender-related issues are of interest to project staff of any gender (Q1)
- The majority of ENACT staff have experience in working on other European-funded projects and most of them responded positively to the question that these projects dealt with gender-related issues such as collection of gender statistics, creation of KPIs to increase participation of women on projects, creation of gender policies and gender equality plan and dissemination among the employees (Q2.1). These examples will be considered in order to propose activities on the ENACT project.
- Some of the project partners are generally aware of the gender-related policies by the European Commission and highlighted several aspects that are part of these policies including gender balance in decision making, addressing gender pay and pension gaps, challenging gender stereotypes, ending gender-based violence and achieving work-life balance for parents (Q3.1). The large majority of the project partners who were not aware of these policies are interested to be informed about this (Q3.2) and this can be achieved through the organisation of a webinar or by distributing information among partners. These activities would be useful for enhancing the knowledge and understanding of all project partners.
- The project partners suggested a range of actions that the project can take in order to increase awareness about and address any gender inequality, discrimination or intimidation including

further discussion on the gender-related issues, adoption of gender-neutral language in presentations and deliverables, promoting the participation of women in research output presentations e.g. conferences and workshops, establishing gender equality KPIs and promoting gender equality, creating a process for reporting and addressing any incidents of gender discrimination or intimidation (Q4.1).

- Some project partners informed that their organisation has a gender equality plan, code of conduct, equality and diversity policy, however most partners reported that they are not aware of policy documents that exist in their own organisation aiming to address gender inequality and improve gender balance (Q5.1). Almost all partners think that it would be good for their organisation to have such documents and provide them to their employees (Q5.2) and this information will be shared amongst the ENACT project consortium.
- A small number of survey participants reported that they had an adverse gender-related personal experience in their organisation which they have either reported (1 case) or did not do anything about (1 case) (Q6.1)
- As a general comment, it has been suggested that all gender identities should be considered in relation to this topic, not only the prevalent ones (male/female) (Q7).

It is intended that the findings of the survey and the actions proposed by the partners be put forward at the next project GA in order to receive due consideration.

It is further intended that another Gender Survey is carried out towards the end of the project to establish whether the responses show any further awareness as well as any changes in the staff attitude towards this topic.

7. Ethics consideration in ENACT

Ethics encompass principles and values guiding moral conduct, crucial in research and innovation to ensure integrity, respect, and accountability. Implementing ethics is vital in EU projects as they ensure that research and innovation endeavors benefit society while minimizing harm, fostering trust among stakeholders, and promoting responsible conduct in accordance with legal and ethical standards.

A list of documents related to ethical, legal, socio-economic and cultures in AI (ELSECAI) are provided in this deliverable to inform consortium partners about ethical and legal issues in design of the ENACT platform and AI models. Two workshops are planned to be conducted based on the information collected in T1.4 (Data Management and Governance, Trustworthy AI, Regulatory, Societal, Ethical and Gender Issues) to train the researchers and end users. First workshop will be conducted in M10 in collaboration with INNO and second workshop will be planned for M18 of the project. Technical and pilot activities will be monitored at each stage of the project to highlight any issues relating to data protection, ethical research, and AI. The following regulatory reforms will also be considered:

1. Data Governance Act¹⁹

¹⁹ Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (Data Governance Act).

2. Artificial Intelligence Act²⁰
3. Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI²¹
4. White Paper on Artificial Intelligence – A European Approach to Excellence and Trust, “Building Trust in Human-Centric AI”²² and the “2030 Digital Compass: The European Way for the Digital Decade”²³.

7.1 Ethics for Trustworthy AI

The Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI have been published by the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (AI-HLEG)²⁴ in 2019. According to these guidelines, trustworthy IA has the following 3 components:

- lawful – compliance with all applicable laws and regulations
- ethical – adherence to ethical principles and values
- robust – from a technical and social perspective not causing any unintentional harm.

AI-HLEG guidelines stipulated the following seven key requirements that the AI systems should achieve to be deemed trustworthy:

1. human agency and oversight
2. technical robustness and safety
3. privacy and data governance
4. transparency
5. diversity, non-discrimination and fairness
6. environmental and societal well-being and
7. accountability

1. Human agency and oversight:

Users should be able to make informed autonomous decisions regarding AI systems. They should be given the knowledge and tools to comprehend and interact with AI systems to a satisfactory degree and, where possible, be enabled to reasonably self-assess or challenge the system. AI systems should support individuals in making better, more informed choices in accordance with their goals. Human oversight helps ensuring that an AI system does not undermine human

²⁰ "Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council Laying Down Harmonized Rules on the Artificial Intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and Amending Certain Union Legislative Acts".

²¹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>

²² 73 White Paper on Artificial Intelligence - A European Approach to Excellence and Trust, “Building Trust in Human-Centric AI”, available at: <https://www.ouvrirlascience.fr/white-paper-on-artificial-intelligence-a-european-approach-to-excellence-and-trust/> (Accessed 06 May 2024).

²³ European Commission, “2030 Digital Compass: the European way for the Digital Decade” (9 March 2021), available at: <https://eufordigital.eu/library/2030-digital-compass-the-european-way-for-the-digital-decade/> (Accessed 06 May 2024).

²⁴ High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, ‘Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI’, available at: {HYPERLINK" <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>"} (Accessed 26 March 2024).

autonomy or causes other adverse effects. Oversight may be achieved through governance mechanisms such as a human-in-the-loop (HITL), human-on-the-loop (HOTL), or human-in-command (HIC) approach.

2. Technical Robustness and safety:

The AI systems should be developed with a preventative approach to risks and in a manner such that they reliably behave as intended while minimising unintentional and unexpected harm, and preventing unacceptable harm. The AI systems should be protected against vulnerabilities that can allow them to be exploited by adversaries, e.g. hacking. The AI systems should have safeguards that enable a fallback plan in case of problems. They need to provide high level of accuracy and their results should be reproducible and reliable.

3. Privacy and data governance:

The AI systems must guarantee privacy and data protection throughout a system's entire lifecycle. This includes the information initially provided by the user, as well as the information generated about the user over the course of their interaction with the system. Only duly qualified personnel with the competence and need to access individual's data should be allowed to do so.

4. Transparency:

The data sets and the processes that yield the AI system's decision, including those of data gathering and data labeling as well as the algorithms used, should be documented to the best possible standard to allow for traceability and an increase in transparency. The decisions made by the AI systems should be understood and traced by human beings. The AI systems should be able to provide a suitable explanation of their decision-making process. Humans have the right to be informed that they are interacting with an AI system. The AI system's capabilities and limitations should be communicated to AI practitioners or end-users in a manner appropriate to the use case at hand.

5. Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness:

Unfair bias must be avoided, as it could lead to unintended (in)direct prejudice and discrimination against certain groups or people, potentially exacerbating prejudice and marginalisation. AI systems should be user-centric and designed in a way that allows all people to use AI products or services, regardless of their age, gender, abilities or characteristics. When designing an AI system it is advisable to consult stakeholders who may directly or indirectly be affected by the system throughout its life cycle.

6. Societal and environmental well-being:

Ideally, AI systems should be used to benefit all human beings, including future generations. They should be sustainable and ecologically responsible, their impact should be assessed from a societal perspective, taking into account its effect on institutions, democracy and society at large.

7. Accountability:

Mechanisms should be put in place to ensure responsibility and accountability for AI systems and their outcomes, both before and after their development, deployment and use. AI systems should be able to be independently audited. The ability to report on actions or decisions that

contribute to a certain system outcome, and to respond to the consequences of such an outcome, must be ensured. When unjust adverse impact occurs, accessible mechanisms should be foreseen to ensure adequate redress. Knowing that redress is possible when things go wrong is key to ensure trust.

The essence of the above 7 guidelines is captured in a set of 13 questions that are used in ENACT to carry out self-assessment of AI developments. Since the AI systems developed in ENACT could be considered as a low-risk system, the focus will be on ensuring the robustness, transparency and security aspects of the AI solution.

Based on the analysis of HLEG guidelines and their implications on the ENACT work program, we have identified four tasks where AI and AI-based solutions will be developed in the ENACT project. In the following subsections, we provide the self-assessments carried out in these tasks, with regards to the AI-HLEG guideline.

7.1.1 T5.1: AI Models for Optimal Performance Predictions in the Compute Continuum [CERTH]

T5.1 Description: In this task, the goal is to develop AI and ML models (CERTH and FDI) able to predict various factors regarding the different systems and algorithms operating in the ENACT CCC. The AI models that will be developed must be able to take into account the characteristics of the specific running software and adapt to changes in the computing environment. Data and metadata from T4.2 related to various CCC aspects that will be monitored there will be fed (through ENACT Data Space infrastructure of T4.4) to T5.1 algorithms as they should be able to predict performance under varying workloads and environmental conditions and suggest optimal configurations for the computing resources. The task will require an understanding of AI and machine learning techniques, as well as knowledge of distributed computing systems and the compute continuum. Regression and classification algorithms alongside genetic algorithms and multi-objective swarm optimization approaches will be employed by this task. Effective communication, collaboration, and problem-solving skills will be essential for success in this task. Special focus will be also given, by DNET and CERTH, to a human-centric approach of AI outcomes. XAI mechanisms such as the computation of AI/ML model metrics and use of libraries like Dalex will be used in order to present to system admins a justification beyond AI predictions and decisions.

The self-assessment for the above task is described below:

- 1. Could the AI system affect the human autonomy and privacy of individuals?**
In general, an AI system could affect both autonomy and privacy of humans. Regarding the forecasting algorithms that will be mainly built in this task there is no foreseen connection with human privacy issues. Regarding autonomy, these predictive algorithms may affect somehow the decision-making progress from system admins that decide for orchestration process in a cloud-edge system.
- 2. Are there measures to ensure the AI system's integrity, robustness and overall security against potential attacks over its lifecycle?**
Yes. In this task the following approaches will be adopted:
 - Model interpretability methods and explainable AI (XAI) approaches to provide insights into the model's decision-making process and features were used for training.

- Data Quality and Security: processes like data cleansing to remove noise and ensure consistency in the training datasets will be applied. Moreover, secure data transfer based on project mechanisms (for example identity management, data connectors etc.) will be used.
- 3. Could the AI system have negative, critical or damaging effects (e.g. to human or societal safety) in case of risks or threats such as design or technical faults, defects, outages, attacks, misuse, inappropriate or malicious use?**

AI systems may have the potential to cause negative, critical, or damaging effects to human and societal safety. Regarding T5.1 this could somehow be related of potential affect in orchestration decision in a compute continuum and provide a kind of a technical fault in Orchestrator. For this reason, some metrics and measurements related to AI models trust and health should be kept and be considered by AI Orchestrator or relevant end users (system admins). The development and implementation of such metrics will be part of the T5.1.
 - 4. Could a low level of accuracy of the AI system result in critical, adversarial or damaging consequences?**

Potentially yes but the adversarial or damaging issues could be mitigated by considering trust, health and interpretability of AI models as described before.
 - 5. Are there measures to ensure that the data (including training data) used to develop the AI system is up-to-date, of high quality, complete and representative of the environment in which the system will be deployed?**

Yes, such measures are being considered in T5.1 and they are mainly related to data quality assessment process. Regarding the algorithms will be developed in this task data pre-processing techniques will be applied to ensure data quality that will be considered during the training phase. Moreover, data-based retraining will be adopted. Data will be monitored, and any significant changes may cause retraining of algorithms.
 - 6. Could the AI system cause critical, adversarial, or damaging consequences (e.g. pertaining to human safety) in case of low reliability and/or reproducibility?**

Yes, low reliability and reproducibility of AI systems can lead to critical, adversarial, or damaging consequences. However, as this task will provide some predictive algorithms to support orchestration functionalists of the project, the predictions can help mitigate the potential damage, making critical consequence more or less an unforeseen case here. The pilot cases where the AI solutions are to be applied are mainly for improving content distribution application and therefore they don't pose significant risks to human as in the case of critical applications, like health applications, autonomous vehicles, industrial automation, financial apps etc.
 - 7. Will the AI system be trained or developed by using or processing personal data (including special categories of personal data)?**

Considering the current requirements and specifications, at this stage the use of personal data is not foreseen in the ENACT pilots as the cases are related to CCC testing in terms of optimal deployment etc. and not to create pilot applications for company's customers and public usage in general. For example, in MOG pilot we will handle some videos of sport games (include people) but the available material is agreed to be shared for internal (with respect to the project scope) use only.

8. Will there be in place measures that address the traceability of the AI system during its entire lifecycle?

Regarding forecasting algorithms of T5.1, there will be measures related to model's performance that will be monitored targeting re-training of the model in the cases that metrics will be decreased.

9. Will there be in place measures to continuously assess the quality of the input data to the AI system?

Yes, data will be monitored, and any significant changes may cause retraining of algorithms.

10. Is there a mechanism that allows for flagging issues related to bias, discrimination or poor performance of the AI system?

As -mentioned above regarding the forecasting algorithms of T5.1 will be measures related to model's performance that will be monitored.

11. Are there potential negative impacts of the AI system on the environment?

Yes, the negative impacts are mainly related to energy consumption of CCC. For example, AI training and inference processes often require significant computational resources, which can lead to increased energy consumption and carbon emissions. However, the target of T5.1 is to predict this type of environmental impact in order to support the optimal orchestration and deployment of services and algorithms in ENACT CCC.²⁵

12. Are there mechanisms that facilitate the AI system's auditability (e.g. traceability of the development process, the sourcing of training data and the logging of the AI system's processes, outcomes, positive and negative impact)?

Yes, some actions related to auditability will take place including the following:

- Documentation of requirements, design specifications, data sources, pre-processing steps, model architectures, hyper-parameters, and evaluation metrics
- Continuous evaluation and validation of task's AI models' performance against predefined criteria, benchmarks, and use case requirements
- Use of version control systems (e.g., Git) to track changes to code, data, and configurations over time.
- Use of explainable AI (XAI) methods to provide insights related to T5.1 forecasting AI models decision-making process.

13. Can independent third parties audit the AI system?

In general, independent third-parties can audit an AI system to enhance transparency, accountability, and trust in AI systems by providing external validation and guidance. In ENACT project there is an External Advisory Board. One of the experts there is planned to be for AI area in order to provide further guidance and feedback related to this matter as well.

²⁵ Upon future implementation of the results of the project, the overall reduction of energy consumption facilitated by the project results will dwarf any energy consumption incurred within the project

7.1.2 T5.2: Graph Neural Networks for Scheduling and Dynamic Optimisation of Hyper-Distributed Applications [UPV]

T5.2 Description: In this task, the design and implementation of ENACT CCC representation as GNN models will take place. The task will build upon T4.2 outcomes (continuum dynamic graph representation) and will create methods that can handle fully dynamic graphs in continuous time and learn distributed scheduling policies for hyper-distributed applications. The model (developed by UPV and ICE) should be able to handle both structure dynamics (such as node/edge addition/deletion) and attribute dynamics (such as node/edge feature changes) as they will be available from WP4. The GNN models should also be able to update its parameters efficiently by using local retraining techniques based on events to strengthen further the cognitive functions of ENACT edge-to-cloud continuum. The model would be evaluated on synthetic and real-world datasets that capture different aspects of graph dynamics by CERTH and INNO.

The self-assessment for the above task is described below:

1. Could the AI system affect the human autonomy and privacy of individuals?

While the T5.2 AI system will not be trained or developed using personal data, its deployment could still potentially impact human autonomy. For instance, if the system is not able to scale properly, services could remain inaccessible over a period of time. This could influence people's choices and behaviors, thereby impacting their autonomy.

2. Are there measures to ensure the AI system's integrity, robustness and overall security against potential attacks over its lifecycle?

Yes, T5.2 AI system will be designed with robust measures to ensure its integrity, resilience, and security throughout its lifecycle. These measures encompass various layers, from initial development to deployment and ongoing maintenance. Continuous monitoring and updates will help to identify and mitigate potential vulnerabilities, ensuring that the system remains resilient against emerging threats.

3. Could the AI system have negative, critical or damaging effects (e.g. to human or societal safety) in case of risks or threats such as design or technical faults, defects, outages, attacks, misuse, inappropriate or malicious use?

Employing machine learning algorithms may carry a significant risk of lacking transparency, though the impact of this risk should be minimal as long as these algorithms do not make substantial decisions that may harm people.

Neglecting to monitor the system performance and results could lead to accountability, transparency, and accuracy issues. The specific makeup or blend of ENACT tools in the future, especially influenced by open-source knowledge, might prove unpredictable and challenging to manage. For that reason, ENACT T5.2 will provide verification and validation methods to evaluate and ensure the reliability, accountability and transparency of the AI system. On the one hand, the documentation will provide the details of the model verification (methodology and results). Moreover, the AI system will include a logging functionality to track its decision-making process and any significant events during operation. This logging functionality will record inputs, outputs, and any intermediate steps taken by the AI system, allowing for transparency and accountability in its actions.

4. Could a low level of accuracy of the AI system result in critical, adversarial or damaging consequences?

In the context of optimizing the deployment and configuration of resources and services in the continuum, a low level of accuracy in the AI system could lead to adversarial consequences. If the AI system's accuracy is affected, it may make suboptimal decisions regarding deployment, leading to inefficiencies, resource wastage, or even system failures. This could have cascading effects on various aspects of the continuum, including performance degradation, increased latency, and reduced reliability. Consequently, services may suffer disruptions, leading to inability to access services, financial losses, operational setbacks, or compromised user experiences. This is especially catastrophic if the affected services manage critical processes. To avoid this, the AI system will generate models following the machine learning process flow. This flow comprises the following steps: data gathering, data cleaning and feature engineering, model building, algorithm selection, and model evaluation. To ensure the accuracy of the model, it will be evaluated using metrics such as ROC-AUC and Mean Average Precision (MAP).

5. Are there measures to ensure that the data (including training data) used to develop the AI system is up-to-date, of high quality, complete and representative of the environment in which the system will be deployed?

Regular data validation processes can be conducted to assess the quality and completeness of the data. This involves verifying the accuracy, relevance, and reliability of the data sources. Moreover, employing diverse and representative datasets that capture the variability and complexity of the deployment environment can enhance the robustness and effectiveness of the AI system. This may involve collecting data from various sources, environments, and scenarios to ensure comprehensive coverage. Furthermore, establishing data governance frameworks and protocols can help to ensure compliance with ethical and regulatory standards while safeguarding data integrity and privacy.

6. Could the AI system cause critical, adversarial, or damaging consequences (e.g. pertaining to human safety) in case of low reliability and/or reproducibility?

In scenarios where the AI system's reliability is low, or its outputs are not reproducible, there is a risk that the services that are controlled by the system will become inaccessible for a period of time or experiencing significant latency. This could lead to adverse consequences, especially if the AI system is controlling the deployment of in critical sectors services like healthcare, autonomous driving, or emergency response systems. T5.2 will implement model evaluation procedures to ensure that model inference maintains high reliability and accuracy.

7. Will the AI system be trained or developed by using or processing personal data (including special categories of personal data)?

No. T5.2 AI system will not be developed using or processing personal data. Instead, the system will leverage the properties of the network of computation nodes composing the cloud-edge continuum. These properties include but are not limited to computational capabilities, latency, bandwidth, and reliability.

8. Will there be in place measures that address the traceability of the AI system during its entire lifecycle?

Yes. On the one hand, comprehensive documentation will be delivered, including design, development, testing, deployment, and maintenance. Additionally, version controlling will permit to track changes made to the AI system's code, data, and configurations over time.

9. Will there be in place measures to continuously assess the quality of the input data to the AI system?

Before running the AI model, there will be a preliminary processing phase followed by an evaluation module to assess the quality.

10. Is there a mechanism that allows for flagging issues related to bias, discrimination or poor performance of the AI system?

Different mechanism will be developed for that purpose. The AI system documentation will include details about its design, data sources, and algorithms used. This will allow data engineers and auditors to understand how the system operates and facilitates identification of potential biases or performance issues. This practice not only builds trust, but also helps to quickly identify and rectify problems of bias or discrimination. Clear documentation and accessible explanations enable stakeholders to review the system effectively and quickly address any deficiencies.

An additional mechanism will enhance the system's integrity. Regular and thorough reviews of datasets will ensure that they are diverse and representative of the features the model serves. By actively monitoring dataset composition, the AI system can maintain fairness and accuracy in its outputs.

11. Are there potential negative impacts of the AI system on the environment?

Running AI models often requires a significant amount of computational resources, which result in environmental impact. However, at the same time, the models developed in this system will permit to orchestrate and optimize the resources in the continuum and therefore to reduce the impact on the carbon footprint of systems that they manage. Although the model inference has an environmental impact, overall, the environmental costs will be reduced.

12. Are there mechanisms that facilitate the AI system's auditability (e.g. traceability of the development process, the sourcing of training data and the logging of the AI system's processes, outcomes, positive and negative impact)?

Datasets and the technology that underlies the system should be documented, e.g. the methodology used for designing and developing the system, the algorithms used during the training, the methods used to test and validate it and the outcomes of the system. Clear records enable auditors to understand how the system was built and identify any potential biases or errors introduced during development.

13. Can independent third parties audit the AI system?

Yes. Independent third parties will be able to access to the project outcomes (deliverables and source code) to evaluate various aspects of the AI system, including its algorithms, data sources, model training processes, and overall performance.

7.1.3 T5.3 GNN & RL-based Orchestrator for Dynamic Deployments in the Compute Continuum [UNP]

T5.3 will develop the Cognitive-Scheduler for Edge-Cloud Continuum that will enhance the open-source KubeEdge system with AI mechanisms (using a combination of graph neural networks (GNN) from T5.2 and reinforcement learning (RL) techniques), enabling the KubeEdge system to make intelligent decisions concerning scheduling, orchestration and optimal deployment of services in the compute continuum. The GNNs (from 5.2) will be responsible for determining and predicting the optimal deployment configuration from the dynamic graphs. They will be trained (by UNP and ICCS) to learn the relationships between different nodes in the graph and use this information to predict the availability and suitability of different resources for specific applications. The DRL will be used by CERTH to optimize the resource allocation decision-making process. The system will learn to make decisions that maximize application performance while minimizing resource utilization and cost as all these functional and non-functional requirements will be set as goals and rewards for the DRL agents. Predictions and optimizations by T5.1 will be also considered. The DRL agent will receive feedback on the decisions it makes in terms of the application's performance metrics, and it will update its policy accordingly to enhance the ENACT system's cognition based on Active Learning approaches (FDI) from T5.4.

The self-assessment for the above task is described below:

Task 5.3 mainly focuses on the orchestration and optimal deployment of services in the compute continuum. This means that no AI is developed within the scope of this task, as the orchestrator is only meant to execute decisions made by the AI coming from Task 5.1 and 5.2. The DRL agent of T5.3 will act over the T5.1 and T5.2 outcomes so what is applied/answered for these two tasks will be followed in this case as well.

7.1.4 T5.4 Virtual Environment for Training, Retraining and Recalibration of AI Models [ICE]

This task will implement research and develop a virtual training environment for GNNs to support the efficient training, retraining and recalibration of distributed and federated AI models to improve accuracy and reliability of AI models that are distributed across multiple nodes in a network. The training environment, developed by ICE and SIE, will also be used for investigating distributed learning mechanisms that can support pilot applications (ARC, SPTD will investigate) by providing collaborative learning and inference without compromising data privacy or network bandwidth. Federated Learning mechanisms will be explored and deployed (by CERTH) for the cases that data transfer and sharing will not be possible through ENACT Data Space (T4.4). AI models will be exchanged only where edge node models will be used to train and update a common 'master' model in the cloud. These models also pose significant challenges for retraining and recalibration techniques, which aim to update the model parameters or outputs based on new data or feedback from edge nodes. This task will be also in close collaboration with T5.1 and T5.3 as well, in order to support retraining needs regarding AI models will be developed in these tasks.

The self-assessment for the above task is described below:

- 1. Could the AI system affect the human autonomy and privacy of individuals?**
No effect on Human Autonomy is expected based on the developed in T5.4. The AI system developed in this task will contain user data but not related to any critical / sensitive topic, and it will comply with GDPR regulations.
- 2. Are there measures to ensure the AI system's integrity, robustness and overall security against potential attacks over its lifecycle?**
The Virtual Training Environment (VTE) will include a user authorisation and data security mechanisms to ensure security against potential attacks.
- 3. Could the AI system have negative, critical or damaging effects (e.g. to human or societal safety) in case of risks or threats such as design or technical faults, defects, outages, attacks, misuse, inappropriate or malicious use?**
The system is not expected to have negative, critical or damaging effects due to design or technical faults since the VTE is used in the training and recalibration of AI/ML models.
- 4. Could a low level of accuracy of the AI system result in critical, adversarial or damaging consequences?**
The system will enable the users to train their own AI models, the potential consequences of an inaccurately trained AI model is therefore an unknown variable and dependent on the AI model or the users planned usage scenario.
- 5. Are there measures to ensure that the data (including training data) used to develop the AI system is up-to-date, of high quality, complete and representative of the environment in which the system will be deployed?**
The VTE will allow the users to upload their own AI models, and train and run these models based on their own training data. It is therefore expected that users will be responsible to ensure their legitimacy and completeness of their own training data and to ensure that the data is up-to-date, of high quality and representative.
- 6. Could the AI system cause critical, adversarial, or damaging consequences (e.g. pertaining to human safety) in case of low reliability and/or reproducibility?**
The VTE is not expected to have any critical, adversarial or damaging consequences as the use of the tool is dependent on AI models that users will bring or the planned usage scenario of each user.
- 7. Will the AI system be trained or developed by using or processing personal data (including special categories of personal data)?**
The tool will provide an environment for the training of AI models, with users able to upload and use their own training data, the use of personal data is therefore dependent on the planned usage scenario of each user and their AI model. There is no limitation on the use of personal data enforced within the ENACT virtual training environment.

8. Will there be in place measures that address the traceability of the AI system during its entire lifecycle?

Yes, an AI explainability function/module will be implemented in the VTE to address traceability aspects of the ENACT Virtual Training Environment

9. Will there be in place measures to continuously assess the quality of the input data to the AI system?

The data to be used in the VTE will be initially assessed upon upload in the tool, to ensure that valid data is present in the training dataset, however there is little assessment in relation to its quality. Features for cleansing datasets upon uploading are provided within the VTE. The cleansing options to replace NULLs are:

- Values by 1's or 0's, depending on the needs of the dataset
- Mean, mode and average values
- Quartiles: min, max, 25% and 75%
- Drop rows
- Propagate values forward or backward

10. Is there a mechanism that allows for flagging issues related to bias, discrimination or poor performance of the AI system?

There will be a feedback feature within the tool, that will allow users to contact the tool owners/developers for support including for issues relating to bias, discrimination or poor performance.

11. Are there potential negative impacts of the AI system on the environment?

Within ENACT there is a focus on the use of AI to automate and optimise distributed deployments of applications and software services, to optimise performance of the application while also optimising energy efficiency. As such, dependent on the produced AI models, there may be negative impacts on the environment if inaccurate AI models are trained or used. However, no environmental concerns can be associated with the use of VTE.

12. Are there mechanisms that facilitate the AI system's auditability (e.g. traceability of the development process, the sourcing of training data and the logging of the AI system's processes, outcomes, positive and negative impact)?

The ENACT VTE will include an AI explainability module which will enable some aspects of traceability of the AI system and provide the ability to explain certain aspects of any produced model. There will also be features that will enable the logging and storage of outcomes (AI models). There is also limited scope within the VTE in relation to the AI systems auditability.

13. Can independent third parties audit the AI system?

There is limited scope for an audit of the AI system within the VTE.

7.2 Analysis of AI self-assessment for the overall ENACT project

The AI developments in the ENACT project are carried out in the technical tasks of WP5. The self-assessment of these tasks in the above sections show full compliance with the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI. Based on the self-assessment of AI solutions, there are no implications foreseen on

the human autonomy and data protection aspects and processing of personal data will be performed following GDPR guidelines (GDPR (Regulation (EU) 2016/679)).

ENACT project will apply model interpretability methods, user authorization, logging functionality and data security to ensure accuracy, safety and reproducibility of AI systems developed within the project. Data pre-processing and re-training (in case of any significant changes) will be performed to avoid manipulation of training data. Several model validation techniques will be applied to tackle problems like model poisoning and evasion. ENACT will provide comprehensive documentation for the developed AI systems and also maintain versioning control to address traceability.

ENACT aims to reduce the impact of AI systems on the environment by supporting optimal orchestration and optimization of resources. There will be an External Advisory Board, they will have access to the deliverables and source code of AI systems to provide further guidance and feedback.

In domains like cloud computing, AI enhances decision-making capabilities without posing risks to humans or the environment. For instance, Kubernetes automates container deployment in cloud infrastructure. In ENACT, AI orchestrator is being used to extend Kubernetes' functionality by enabling it to consider additional parameters for decision-making at runtime.

This effectively conveys the idea, as developed in ENACT, that AI serves to optimize processes and enhance efficiency within specific contexts, contributing to advancements in technology without compromising safety or ethics.

8. Conclusion

This deliverable is the first version of Data Management Plan of the ENACT project following Horizon Europe's open data requirements. It is documented by T1.4 partners with contribution from the consortium members. This presents initial information collected by M5 of the project, as more technical details related to data management plan, requirements and architecture of the project are not finalized yet.

This DMP document sets up guidelines for the consortium partners to follow for data collection, processing and generation based on FAIR data principles. This approach is to make sure that ENACT project results and data remains open and accessible after the end of project. Data with no sharing restrictions will be made available through trusted repositories such as Zenodo. Data with privacy concerns will remain confidential and protected in accordance with GDPR regulations and ethical standards.

AI systems delivered within ENACT are analyzed based on a trustworthy AI system following HLEG guidelines. Information collected related to trustworthy AI is preliminary at the moment and will be

updated. Two workshops will be organized to ensure continuous transfer of knowledge to consortium partners related to ethics, FAIR data principles and trustworthy AI.

The DMP will be a live document which will be available to consortium partners and will be updated throughout the project. Further information will be collected from partners related actual technical achievements and deliverables. To include the recent developments, final version of DMP will be released at the end of the project in M36.

9. List of Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CA	Consortium Agreement
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ALTAI	Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
AI-HLEG	High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence
ELSECAI	Ethics, Legal, Socio economics, and Cultures in Artificial Intelligence
CCC	Cloud Computing Continuum
GBs	Gigabytes
TBD	To Be Discussed
UC	Use Case
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SOTA	State of the Art
VTE	Virtual Environment for Training
WP	Work Package